

Comparative Analysis of Standard and Casting Resins in mSLA 3D Printing for Precision Lost Wax Casting Applications

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Abstract

This study investigates the integration of modern 3D printing technologies with traditional precision casting methods, specifically exploring the application of mSLA (masked Stereolithography) printing as an alternative to conventional wax model preparation in the lost wax casting process. Two types of UV-curable resins—standard and wax-like casting resin—were comparatively evaluated for dimensional accuracy, surface quality, and casting defects. Models were printed using an Elegoo Mars 2 printer, converted to metal castings via the lost wax method, and subjected to comprehensive dimensional analysis using 3D scanning and GOM Inspect software. Results demonstrate that 3D printed models maintain high dimensional accuracy regardless of their placement on the printing platform, with deviations generally within ± 0.1 mm. The casting resin models yielded superior castings with fewer defects compared to standard resin, which left ash residue during burnout causing porosity and underfilling issues. While the higher cost of specialized casting resins presents a limitation, their performance advantages make the mSLA printing technique particularly suitable for small-batch production and complex geometries in jewelry making and precision engineering applications where traditional manufacturing methods prove challenging.

Keywords

Precision Casting, Lost Wax Method, mSLA 3D Printing Technology, Dimensional Accuracy Analysis, Casting Resins

1 Precision Casting

Precision casting is not a single casting technique but encompasses a range of technologies. Conventionally, it is assumed that these are all techniques that allow for achieving surface roughness of $Ra \leq 10\text{-}20 \mu\text{m}$. Such low roughness is obtained through precise machining (Table 1) or finishing processes, which makes it impossible to achieve in traditional sand molds. Methods capable of achieving the desired roughness and classified as precision casting include: lost wax method, pressure casting, gypsum mold casting, ceramic mold casting, and shell mold casting. Each of these methods has specific applications, and its selection depends on several factors such as the metal material, dimensions, shape and weight of the casting, requirements, production series size, repeatability, and foundry equipment.

Table 1: Surface roughness achievable by various methods

Roughness class	Type of processing	Ra	Rz
1	Rough machining	80	320
2	Medium precision machining	40	160
3	Precise machining	20	80
4	Precise machining	10	40
5	Finishing processing	5	20
6	Finishing processing	2.5	10
7	Rough grinding	1.25	6.3
8	Precise grinding	0.63	3.2
9	Finish grinding	0.32	1.6
10	Lapping	0.16	0.8
11	Polishing paste lapping	0.08	0.4
12	Honing	0.04	0.2
13	Polishing	0.02	0.1
14	Polishing	0.01	0.05

2 Lost Wax Casting Method

The lost wax casting method has been known to humanity for centuries. Initially, it was used for artistic and decorative castings; however, by the 19th century, it began to be utilized in dental prosthetics and was later employed during World War II for weapon production. This method involves creating a wax model of the casting to which the gating system is added and attached to a base. The model is then placed in a mold filled with gypsum or ceramic. Once the mold dries, the wax model is removed by melting it in specially designed machines, and the mold is annealed in a furnace. The annealed mold is then filled with molten metal using one of three methods: gravitationally, centrifugally, or under additional pressure.

2.1 Model Preparation

In traditional lost wax casting, the prototype of the casting—usually made of metal using any technique—is placed between two silicone rubbers, which are then pressed together. After cutting the rubber and removing the model, the mold is ready for creating wax casts. Liquid wax is injected into the mold under pressure using a wax injector; once solidified, a ready wax model is obtained. During this study, this process was omitted and replaced with 3D printing technology. The models were already prepared for connection with gating systems.

2.2 Creating the Mold

Ready wax models or 3D-printed ones must be connected to gating systems. This can be done using pre-made wax rods or by creating them with a mold and wax injector, similar to the models themselves. To connect the models to the gating system, soldering irons with various tips are used, allowing for quick and precise joining of both elements of the casting. Using 3D printing technology, it

would also be possible to print the entire model along with the gating system, improving repeatability and accuracy due to fewer variables in mold preparation.

The completed elements with the gating system are attached to the mold base using soldering irons and wax. Then, the remaining part of the mold made of metal is applied to the base. This prepared mold is filled with a mixture of gypsum and water in a 4:1 ratio, which was prepared and poured using a vacuum mixer for better results. After pouring gypsum, the molds were left to dry and then separated from their rubber bases.

2.3 Burnout Process

The dried molds still contain models inside them. To remove these models, they must first be placed in a machine called a wax injector to melt all the wax. Molds without wax models must then be placed in a furnace for annealing. This process can take several hours to even dozens of hours depending on the materials used. When using models made not from wax but with 3D printing technology, this process differs slightly. Models made from polymers or resins are not melted before placing molds in the furnace; instead, the annealing process also serves to remove the model from inside the mold.

3 Centrifugal Casting Process

The final stage of lost wax casting was centrifugal casting, one of the techniques that allows for achieving precise castings through centrifugal force. Centrifugal casting is classified into three types: true centrifugal casting semi-centrifugal casting, and pressure-assisted centrifugal casting. True centrifugal casting is used for producing castings with rotational symmetry, where the external surface is shaped by the rotating mold while the internal surface is cylindrical, shaped by centrifugal force. In semi-centrifugal casting, the internal surface is shaped by a core inside the mold—usually sand—which allows for achieving any internal shape. In pressure-assisted centrifugal casting, the gating system is located at the axis of rotation where centrifugal force aids in filling the mold with molten metal. Disposable molds are commonly used in this method.

During this study, centrifugal casting was performed as follows: The annealed mold was placed in a centrifugal casting furnace at a designated location. Next, a crucible containing a measured portion of metal granules was placed inside the furnace. After positioning all elements correctly and closing the lid, an induction coil was moved closer to liquefy the metal. Once melted, the coil was lowered, automatically activating furnace rotation. Through centrifugal force generated this way, the crucible moved toward the mold, forcing liquid metal into it. After stopping rotation, the mold was removed and left for a certain time depending on its mass so that the metal inside could solidify. The final step involved placing the mold in water to dissolve all gypsum and release the finished casting.

4 3D Printing Technology mSLA

This chapter is dedicated to one of the newest techniques used in industry: 3D printing. This technology was invented in the second half of the 20th century and patented by Charles W. Hull. It has been continuously developed to this day. 3D printing has enabled engineers to create geometries that are very difficult or even impossible to achieve using traditional methods, which has further contributed to its development. In recent years, this method has become extremely popular due to the decreasing cost of devices and their ease of use, allowing them to be utilized even in home environments.

4.1 Materials Used in the Study

Two UV-curable resins from Anycubic and Phrozen were used during the study:

Anycubic Resin(Figure 1):

This resin is classified as a standard resin, meaning it does not have any special physical or chemical properties distinguishing it from other resins available on the market. It is commonly used in mSLA printing, which is why it was included in this study.

The wavelength required for curing this resin is 405 nm, a parameter determined by the printer used and strictly specified by the manufacturer.

Exposure times provided by the manufacturer are as follows: initial layers require between 20-80 seconds, while subsequent layers need between 3-15 seconds.

Phrozen Resin (Wax-like) (Figure 2):

This resin is designed for casting and is described by the manufacturer as "wax-like," meaning that models printed with this resin exhibit properties similar to those made from wax.

The exposure times for this resin were determined experimentally: 45 seconds for initial layers and 4.5 seconds for subsequent layers.

Figure 1: Anycubic classic resin

Figure 2: Phrozen casting resin

4.2 3D Printer Used in the Study

The printer used for this study was an Elegoo Mars 2 (Figure 3), which operates using mSLA technology: It features a 6-inch monochromatic LCD screen emitting light at a wavelength of 405 nm.

The working area dimensions are 129x80x150 mm, sufficient for printing the components used in this study.

Printing speed varies between 30-50 mm/h depending on the resin used.

Figure 3: Elegoo Mars 2

5 Results Analysis

All printed models and castings were subjected to 3D scanning. The resulting three-dimensional models, saved in STL format, were compared using GOM Inspect software. The comparison process involved:

1. Importing the reference geometry file.
2. Updating the mesh model to match the CAD model.
3. Importing the geometry file for comparison.
4. Aligning models through automatic fitting.
5. Inspecting deviations between the compared model and reference geometry.
6. Adding flags with deviation values.
7. Generating a table containing deviation data.

5.1 Comparison of Models Depending on Placement on the Working Plane

The first comparison of models concerns checking whether the arrangement of models on the table has a significant impact on the dimensional accuracy of the prints. The models were placed on the working table in a triangle to check the extreme positions on the x and y axes.

The model scans were compared with each other, "each with each," to best determine the impact of model arrangement on the working table on dimensional accuracy. For easier identification of which model will be discussed, the prints were assigned numbers (Figure 4) from 1 to 3 starting from the right side.

Figure 4: Models numbers

The first two models 1 and 2 at first glance do not show large dimensional deviations between them. Most deviations are in the range of 0.00-(-0.08), which, considering the inaccuracies resulting from scanning and basing models relative to each other, are deviations that can be considered systematic errors that will not affect the actual result.

There are also two deviations with much higher values, +0.38 and -0.47 (Figure 5). These are random errors resulting from errors during scanning or model import, and are ultimately not considered in the results. Across the entire model surface, there are no large dimensional deviations between models; the resulting deviations are within the tolerance range of error. However, there are places where these deviations are slightly larger, measuring a tenth of a millimeter.

Figure 5: Inspection of models with dimensional flags applied for signet rings 1 and 2

These deviations are found in places where there are recesses in the model. These results may suggest that model placement may matter for very precise models with complex geometry, or during scanning, certain variables occurred that introduced these errors, e.g., changes in lighting.

The next two models, 1 and 3, allow for determining dimensional deviations of models placed at two opposite ends of the working table. In this case, the results are similar to the comparison of models 1 and 2. However, in this case, there are no random errors, which may indicate a smaller dimensional difference. The deviations in this test largely fall within <0.1 mm, and deviations greater than 0.1 mm (Figure6) again occur in recesses, which presents a characteristic feature and may mean that deviations in these areas result from errors arising from 3D scanning.

Figure 6: Inspection of models with dimensional flags applied for signet rings 1 and 3

The last comparison of signets 2 and 3 shows that between the two last models, there are no dimensional deviations greater than 0.1 mm, except for places on the backs of the signets (Figure 7) where there are clear deviations. However, these are related to the inaccurate removal of supports, so they were omitted in the assessment of dimensional accuracy.

The absence of deviations greater than 0.1 mm suggests that in model 1, deviations of greater values occurring in recesses result from scanning errors and can be rejected under certain conditions. To be certain, this stage of the study would need to be repeated, but due to the high cost of casting resin, this was not done. All deviations occurring on the models allow us to conclude that the arrangement of elements on the table does not significantly affect the dimensional accuracy of printed models.

Figure 7: Inspection of models with dimensional flags applied for signet rings 1 and 3

5.2 Comparison of Models Printed Using Casting Resin Versus CAD Model

In this section, models printed with casting resin were scanned and compared to their CAD counterparts using GOM Inspect software.

5.3 Comparison of Signet Models

To determine the dimensional accuracy of individual prints, it is necessary to compare them to the ideal CAD model. Thanks to this procedure, we will be able to determine exact deviations depending on the material used. Since it was established that the placement of the model on the working field does not significantly affect dimensional accuracy, only two signets were selected (one of each type of resin), which is sufficient to determine dimensional accuracy in relation to the CAD model.

The model made of casting resin mostly has positive deviations, which may prove desirable during the casting process due to material shrinkage. There were also very large positive deviations, which are a random error resulting from a large recess in the model, making it impossible for the scanner to accurately reproduce the print surface. A significant majority of deviations are within ± 0.1 mm, which indicates high print accuracy.

However, it is not free from defects that cause deviations at a level above 0.2 mm. They occur, however, on convex elements, which, similar to positive deviations throughout the model, may be beneficial during casting as the greatest shrinkage may potentially occur in these places.

The situation is completely different with the model made of classic resin (Figure 8), which has both positive and negative deviations, making them more difficult to eliminate both in the printing process and

the subsequent casting process. In this case, very high positive deviations also occurred inside the signet related to the scanning process itself and were also rejected.

However, quite high negative deviations appeared on the bottom of the ring, exceeding 0.3 mm in places. Such large deviations concentrated in one place may also suggest random errors or may be the result of the printing process itself, as the model separated from the supports in these places, so we cannot unequivocally determine whether these results are an error.

Figure 8: Comparison of the Scan of a Signet Ring Made from Classic Resin with the CAD Model

6 Comparison of Models from Two Resins Between Themselves

Comparing models made from two different resins will allow us to determine at such an early stage whether the material used to make the model can have a significant impact on the dimensional accuracy of the final model.

6.1 Comparison of Signet Models

The comparison of models initially indicates that there are no significant deviations between models made from two different materials. Point inspection (Figure 9) confirms the observation; deviations are within ± 0.18 mm.

However, there are places where these deviations are much larger and exceed even 2 mm, but this results from scanning inaccuracies, which was noticed during the comparison of previous models, so these deviations were omitted. The absence of other deviations greater than 0.18 mm allows us to conclude that the material used to make the model does not affect the dimensional accuracy of the model, and thus the castings themselves should not differ significantly.

Figure 9: Comparison of the Scan of a Signet Ring Made from Classic Resin with the CAD Model

7 Comparison of Castings to the CAD Model

As part of the work, six castings were made of three elements: a signet, an ear cast, and an oil swirler. Each of these elements was cast twice in a mold made using a printed model of casting resin and classic resin. Scans of these castings were compared in the GOM Inspect program.

7.1 Comparison of Signet Models

The first signet model was cast in a mold made using a classic resin model. The deviation flags applied to it indicate very small deviations from the CAD model. Despite predictions about eliminating positive deviations by the shrinkage of the material from which it was cast, this did not happen (Figure 10).

However, a certain relationship can be observed: at the top of the casting, where the geometry is more complicated, there are positive deviations mostly not exceeding +0.14 mm. However, in the lower part of the casting on a large flat surface, these deviations are mostly negative and do not exceed -0.1 mm. As in previous comparisons, there are very large deviations related to errors during scanning, and like before, they are not taken into account.

The entire model shows very slight dimensional deviations from the CAD model, which indicates the good quality of the mold made. Although imperfections are not visible on the scan, they appear in the final casting. The main casting defect that occurred during casting was porosity, which appeared both on the inner surface of the signet and on the lion's head itself. They could have been caused by remaining ash from the model created during the burning process. Unfortunately, these are defects that disqualify the casting in precision casting due to the difficult or even impossible process of repairing the casting.

The casting made in the mold for which classic resin was used was not deprived of the gating system, which is visible on the scan. However, the deviations contained on it were not taken into account in the study. The casting itself has a small number of defects that do not disqualify it, which was the case with the previous casting. At the same time, dimensional deviations are much smaller and largely contained below 0.1 mm, which may indicate that in this case, the prediction related to eliminating positive deviations from the model by material shrinkage has been confirmed.

Figure 10: Inspection of Models with Dimensional Flags Applied for the Cast Made from Classic Resin

7.2 Comparison of Ear Cast Models

Analyzing the castings of the inner ear, we can notice certain features recurring from the signets related to the use of different materials for mold models.

In the casting for which classic resin was used, the surface reproduction at the end of the ear canal is very inaccurate, which, as in the case of the signet, may be related to remaining ash. Additionally, the casting itself has very large and varied dimensional deviations across the entire surface (Figure 11), which significantly hinders their compensation when attempting to make a mold and casting again. Unfortunately, porosity also appeared (Figure 56), but this time they occurred on a surface that is suitable for repair and does not disqualify the casting.

In the case of the casting made from casting resin, the casting has an overflow that could have been created by a cracked mold or by the plaster not filling this space during pouring. Despite this defect, the casting in this form has much smaller deviations, which are mostly positive, allowing for easy model correction. Large deviations on the bottom of the model are related to the need to repair the 3D scan in the GOM Inspect program, and for this reason, they cannot be taken into account when developing the results. In the case of this model, the surface of the end of the ear canal was reproduced very well (Figure 59), which may confirm the suspicions that when burning classic resin, a certain amount of ash remains, which affects inaccuracies in castings.

Figure 11: Inspection of the Cast Made from Classic Resin of the Inner Ear

7.3 Comparison of Oil Swirler Models

The last models were castings of an oil swirler which, due to the geometry difficult to obtain by other methods, was an excellent example of the application of precision casting.

In the casting from classic resin, the dimensional deviations are relatively small, and most of them are positive (Figure 12), which positively affects the quality of the casting and the possibility of its correction. However, there are overflows on the flange surface, which may hinder its application or the finishing process. This is not its only flaw, as on the surface located at the inlet, one can observe the formation of dross, which may or may not cause its disqualification as a precision casting.

For the casting from casting resin, the dimensional deviations are positive and mostly do not exceed 0.2 mm. Deviations with a high value, as in the case of the inner ear, are related to the need to repair the scan in the program and are not taken into account. Unfortunately, the scan shows a considerable amount of porosity, but these are small values, and due to having an allowance of material, it can be subjected to finishing processing, which should mostly remove these defects.

Figure 12: Inspection of the Oil Swirler Cast Made from Classic Resin

8 Data Analysis from GOM Inspect Program

The GOM Inspect program allows us to export a table with the values of deviations visible on the dimension flags. By presenting the data in this way, they are more readable, and comparing them with each other requires less work. Additionally, in Excel, we can perform operations that will allow us to calculate the sum of deviations of individual models as well as their standard deviation, MAE, RMSE, and ME. The collected data was placed in a summary table (Table 2) to make the results more readable.

Table 2: Sum, standard deviation, MAE, RMSE, and ME for individual models.

Model	Sum	Standard Deviation	MAE	RMSE	ME
signet 1 -CAD	18.08	0.182	0.16	0.218	0.029
signet 2 -CAD	4.6	0.353	0.266	0.353	0.046
signet 3 -CAD	24.46	0.422	0.324	0.44	0.06
signet 4 -CAD	5.94	0.137	0.097	0.141	0.02
signet 1-2	-2.15	0.106	0.077	0.117	0.033
signet 1-3	-0.87	0.039	0.031	0.046	0.013
signet 2-3	0.32	0.046	0.036	0.046	0.015
Oil swirler - classic	12.61	0.261	0.184	0.294	0.053
Oil swirler - casting	6.99	0.286	0.215	0.295	0.059
Inner ear - classic	9.79	0.381	0.296	0.387	0.066
Inner ear - casting	31.6	0.36	0.324	0.432	0.062
signet - casting - classic	13.7	0.243	0.14	0.26	0.04
signet - casting - casting resin	6.84	0.083	0.098	0.112	0.017

9 Conclusions

1. Models with complex geometry can be obtained through the use of 3D printing technology.
2. Classic resins leave a large amount of ash during burning, which negatively affects the final castings causing porosity and underfilling.
3. The 3D printing process using casting resin is more difficult due to parameters that are difficult to set, requiring several or even a dozen attempts, and due to the susceptibility of the printed model to detach from the printer's working table.
4. 3D printing in mSLA technology ensures very high dimensional accuracy and detail reproduction, which makes it excellent for the jewelry industry.
5. The arrangement of printed elements on the working table does not affect their accuracy, which means we can print more objects at the same time, as the printing time is affected only by the number of layers and not the number of models.
6. Prints in FDM technology have different accuracy depending on the direction of layer application, which can cause dimensional errors that are difficult to correct. In mSLA technology, this problem does not occur, making it easy to eliminate any errors resulting from the shrinkage of both the material from which we make the print and the material from which the model will be cast.
7. Thanks to the possibility of easily applying dimensional changes to the 3D model in any CAD program, the process of creating new molds is significantly accelerated.
8. Due to the printing time, this technique loses to the creation of wax models in mass production; however, it is ideal for unit and small-series production where models often undergo changes.
9. A huge disadvantage of using casting resins is their price, which can be even ten times higher than classic resins.

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